

Dynamic behavior of pneumatic structure with progressively increasing local deformation under wind pressure

Yusuke MIURA *, Toku NISHIMURA^a

* School of Architecture, Kanazawa Institute of Technology
 3-1 Yatsukaho, Hakusan, Ishikawa, Japan
 c1124138@planet.kanazawa-it.ac.jp

^a College of Architecture, Department of Architecture, Kanazawa Institute of Technology

Abstract

Pneumatic structures are lightweight structures that provide internal pressure and maintain in-plane stiffness. On the other hand, the out-of-plane stiffness is low, so the membrane surface must be reinforced with cables. The reference wind speed in a Japanese design recommendation is assumed a return period of 50~1000 years and Gumbel distribution. Through allowable stress design, verifying that the pneumatic structures will not exceed their damage limit due to wind force with a return period of 50 years is necessary. Research into the local behavior of pneumatic structures in strong winds is underway. This study investigated the dynamic behavior of a pneumatic structure under constant internal pressure inflation and subjected to wind forces with a return period of 50 years discussed. The model has a planar geometry of 120 meters and is discretized by plane stress element. The membrane material is PTFE and the cable is wire ropes for structure. The wind pressure coefficients are predicted by machine learning and varies with successive deformations. After inflation with 300Pa, the wind pressure fluctuates harmonically on the positive side, whose frequency is 1 Hz. Principal stress at the apex converges 55% of the tensile strength σ_u . Windward principal stress progressively grows and reaches more than 90% of the tensile strength. It is necessary to examine whether similar results can be obtained at higher internal pressure settings and with wind pressures of different frequency components.

Keywords: pneumatic structure, local deformation, principal stress, instability, return period, strong wind, machine-learning

1. Introduction

Pneumatic structures are lightweight structures that maintain in-plane stiffness by supplying internal pressure. On the other hand, the out-of-plane stiffness is low, requiring the membrane surface to be reinforced with cables. Even if the reinforcement prevents overall instability against strong winds, sustained local deformation can damage the membrane surface. Although the basic wind velocity assumed in structural design has a return period of 50~1000 years [1], it is difficult to say that the critical wind velocity that prevents the collapse of a pneumatic structure is equivalent to the wind velocity over the return period.

Kishimoto et al.[2] investigated the dynamic behavior of a 120m-diameter, rise/span=0.115, circular, flat-boundary, non-reinforced pneumatic structure under variable wind pressure after inflation. Even though the cyclic wind pressure with a return period of 50 years is subjected, the maximum value of the principal stress near the apex is about 90%. Furthermore, the principal stress on the upwind side gradually increases periodically and exceeds the tensile strength. However, this result is based on an analysis with a constant wind pressure coefficient. When a pneumatic structure subjected to strong winds undergoes large out-of-plane deformation, the wind pressure distribution may differ from that of the initial shape. Kato and Maruta [3],[4] examined the need to consider the wind pressure multiplier due

to the deformation of the flexible model in high winds for the rigid model in wind tunnel tests of two different models, a rigid model and a flexible model. The multipliers were 1.2 to 1.3 times for both positive and negative mean wind pressure coefficients, and Peak wind pressure coefficients were 1.1 times for positive pressure 1.5~2.0 times for negative pressure. From this experiment, the wind pressure distribution states the need to consider the deformation of the pneumatic structure and the internal pressure level that stabilizes the structure. PAULETTI and ROCHA incorporated an effective wrinkling criterion into Argyris' triangular membrane element and derived a new expression for pneumatic stiffness[5]. The wind pressure distribution should depend on the shape of the membrane surface. What strategies are less computationally intensive than Large Eddy Simulation or without wind tunnel tests[6]?

In this study, data on the average external pressure coefficient to the rise/span ratio is machine-learned. The regression learner predicts the external pressure coefficient from the deformed shape of pneumatic structures. We investigate the dynamic behavior to utilize the regression learner.

2. Basic equations for stress analysis[7]

2.1. Membrane structure modeling and coordinate system

The membrane surface is a discretized set of triangular elements (Figure 1(a)). The coordinate system set up in the analysis is the one in which one element is extracted from the global coordinate system as shown in Figure 1(b), and this is the local coordinate system. In the local coordinate system, the origin is node 1, the x axis is the direction of node 2, and the y and z axes are the coordinate axes of the Cartesian right-hand system. The element has three translational degrees of freedom. One is in the x direction at node 2 and others are in the x and y directions at node 3. The displacement vector of the element in the local coordinate system is shown in the following equation.

Figure 1: Coordinate system and plane element

$$\mathbf{d} = [u_2 \quad u_3 \quad v_3]^T \quad (1)$$

The nodal displacement vector for each node 3 degrees of freedom in the global coordinate system is shown in the following equation.

$$\mathbf{D} = [U_1 \quad V_1 \quad W_1 \quad U_2 \quad V_2 \quad W_2 \quad U_3 \quad V_3 \quad W_3]^T \quad (2)$$

2.2. Shape functions and stress-strain relationships

The triangular element deformation is assumed to be a planar stress state. The following linear shape functions are used to be compatible the boundary conditions at the element ends:

$$\mathbf{u}(x, y) = [x \quad y] \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\gamma} & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{y}{\alpha} & \frac{1}{\beta} & \frac{y}{\beta} \\ -\frac{\alpha}{\gamma\beta} & \frac{1}{\beta} & \frac{y}{\beta} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_2 \\ u_3 \\ v_a \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The strain-displacement relationship can be expressed in term of Green strain by the following incremental equation:

$$\Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \mathbf{B} \Delta \mathbf{d} = (\mathbf{B}_L + \mathbf{B}_{NL}) \Delta \mathbf{d} \quad (4)$$

Δ denotes increment. \mathbf{B}_L and \mathbf{B}_{NL} are the linear and nonlinear terms of the strain-displacement matrix \mathbf{B} , respectively. The nonlinear term varies with element displacement \mathbf{d} . Figure 2 shows the principal axis of each membrane element, i.e. the fiber direction of the base fabric. The x^* and the y^* mean the directions as the warp and the weft, respectively. The membrane material resists uni-axially, and Figure 3 represents its simplified constitutive law. The stress-strain relationship and the reciprocal law for orthotropic anisotropic materials are shown in Equations (5) and (6).

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^* = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x^* \\ \sigma_y^* \\ \tau_{xy}^* \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_x^*}{1-\nu_x^* \nu_y^*} & \frac{\nu_y^* E_x^*}{1-\nu_x^* \nu_y^*} & 0 \\ \frac{\nu_x^* E_y^*}{1-\nu_x^* \nu_y^*} & \frac{E_y^*}{1-\nu_x^* \nu_y^*} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{xy}^* \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^* \\ \varepsilon_y^* \\ \gamma_{xy}^* \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{C}^* \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^* \quad (5)$$

$$\nu_y^* E_x^* = \nu_x^* E_y^* \quad (6)$$

E_x^* , E_y^* , ν_x^* , ν_y^* and G_{xy}^* are Young modulus, Poisson ratio, and shear modulus, respectively.

Figure 2: Principal coordinate and local coordinates

Figure 3: Stress-strain relation

2.3. Transformation for global and local coordinate systems

Figure 4 illustrates element displacements in the global coordinates X - Y - Z and the local coordinates x - y - z . The dashed line represents the initial position, and let the position of the triangle element be at the n th step. The following equation expresses the relationship between the global and the local coordinates.

$$\mathbf{e}_L = \mathbf{R}(\theta_X, \theta_Y, \theta_Z) \mathbf{e}_G \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{e}_G and \mathbf{e}_L are the unit base vectors in X - Y - Z and x - y - z . \mathbf{R} is the 3×3 transformation matrix that rotates θ_X , θ_Y , θ_Z around the X , Y and Z axes of the global coordinate system, in that order.

Due to the geometric relationship in Figure 4, the relationship between the local coordinate displacement \mathbf{d} and the global coordinate displacement \mathbf{D} can be written the following incremental form:

$$\Delta \mathbf{d} = \mathbf{T} \Delta \mathbf{D} \quad (8)$$

\mathbf{T} in equation (8) is obtained by the following two equations.

$$\mathbf{T} = [-(\mathbf{T}_A + \mathbf{T}_B) \quad \mathbf{T}_A \quad \mathbf{T}_B] \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{T}_A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\beta+v_3}{\gamma+u_2} & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{\alpha+u_3}{\gamma+u_2} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}, \quad \mathbf{T}_B = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{R} \quad (10)$$

Figure 5 shows the element end forces, whose components are denoted in Equations (13) and (14), respectively.

$$\mathbf{p} = [p_{2x} \quad p_{3x} \quad p_{3y}]^T \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{P} = [P_{1X} \quad P_{1Y} \quad P_{1Z} \quad P_{2X} \quad P_{2Y} \quad P_{2Z} \quad P_{3X} \quad P_{3Y} \quad P_{3Z}]^T \quad (12)$$

Contra-gradient law yields the following equilibrium equation:

$$\mathbf{P} = \mathbf{T}^T \mathbf{p} \quad (13)$$

Figure 4: Displacements in the global and the local coordinates

Figure 5: Element end forces

2.4. Element stiffness equation

The incremental form of the Equation (13) is written

$$\Delta \mathbf{P} = \Delta \mathbf{T}^T \mathbf{p} + \mathbf{T}^T \Delta \mathbf{p} \quad (14)$$

The increment of element end force $\Delta \mathbf{p}$ can be expressed from the stiffness equation for the local coordinate.

$$\Delta \mathbf{p} = \mathbf{k} \Delta \mathbf{d} \quad (15)$$

\mathbf{k} denotes the tangent stiffness matrix in local coordinates and consists of linear, initial displacement and geometric matrixes. Substituting Equations (8) and (15) into Equation (14) yields the stiffness equation in the global coordinates

$$\Delta \mathbf{P} = \mathbf{K} \Delta \mathbf{D} \quad (16)$$

where \mathbf{K} is the tangential stiffness matrix in the global coordinates.

3. Dynamic analysis of pneumatic structure subjected to wind pressure depending on deformation

3.1. Wind load

Figure 6 shows the reference wind speeds for each return period. The reference wind speed for the 50-year return period considered as the short-term allowable stress design is 37 m/s. Velocity pressure is based on the wind load-related provisions of the Building Standard Law.

$$q = 0.6EV_0^2, E = E_r^2 G_f \tag{17}$$

where V_0, E_r, G_f are coefficients of reference wind speed, coefficients of average wind speed distribution in height direction, and gust effect factor. The building dimensions are $D = 120\text{m}, h = 20\text{m}, f = 23\text{m}, H = h + f/2 = 33.5\text{m}$ in Figure 7. After inflating analysis, the wind pressure with a return period of 50 years acts using a harmonic action depicted in Figure 7 with 1Hz to investigate the possibility of resonance. The domain classification of the external pressure coefficient of the target Pneumatic structure is shown in Figure 8. From windward, $R_a = -0.075, R_b = -0.26, R_c = -0.49, R_d = 0$

Figure 6: Annual maximum wind speed[8]

Figure 7: Time history of wind pressure

Figure 8: Mean external pressure coefficient [9]

respectively. These coefficients are varied according to the deformation using the method described in the next section.

3.2. Prediction of external pressure coefficient by machine learning

In this study, a machine learning algorithm using MATLAB will be implemented to predict the external pressure coefficient, and a model will be constructed to analyze the data. The algorithm employed in this study is an efficient liner SVM and will be implemented according to the following steps.

I. Supervised data is selected and key variables that influence the prediction of the external pressure coefficient are selected. The primary data used for machine learning is the average external pressure coefficient[1] of spherical roofs by rise/span ratio and nodal coordinates to be trained.

II. Obtain the coordinates of the updated membrane surface from the dynamic analysis.

III. The obtained coordinates are input to the learner in I to obtain an estimate of the average external pressure coefficient.

IV. The wind load is updated from the new average external pressure coefficient.

We employed linear SVM had the lowest mean square error (RMSE) among algorithms. The learned results are shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Learned data and estimation

3.3. Analysis conditions

In this dynamic analysis, the Newmark- β method ($\beta = 1/4$) is used. The time increment is set to 0.01s until the end of inflation and thereafter 0.05s.

Figure 10 shows the initial configuration deflated. The overall plan diameter is 120 m. The membrane material used is class A FGT-1000, with a tensile strength σ_u of $1.64 \times 10^8 \text{N/m}^2$. The cable used is a structural spiral rope (1×127) with a rope diameter of 50 mm. Other material properties of the membrane material are shown in Table 1. The number of nodes is 517, the number of elements is 952, and the boundary nodes are fixed. The damping is Rayleigh type with a damping constant of 5% for the first-order mode of the initial shape. The internal pressure is set to 300N/m^2 in constant. The internal pressure is applied at the inflation for 60 seconds, followed by the wind force for 60 seconds.

Table 1: Analysis condition

Diameter	120m	
Young Modulus	Warp	$9.807 \times 10^5 \text{N/m}^2$
	Weft	$6.867 \times 10^5 \text{N/m}^2$
Poisson ratio	Warp	0.63
	Weft	0.45
Shear modulus	$6.374 \times 10^4 \text{N/m}^2$	
Thickness	1mm	
Tensile strength	$1.64 \times 10^8 \text{N/m}^2$	
Normal internal pressure	300N/m ²	

Fig.10: Initial configuration

Table 2: Cable

Cable type	Structural Spiral rope
Rope diameter	50mm
Unit Weight	12.6kg/m
Young Modulus	$1.65 \times 10^{11} \text{N/m}^2$

3.4. Analysis result

Figure 11 shows the natural mode at the end of inflation, which is the mode that causes unevenness in the center of the span. The natural frequencies are 1.46Hz for the 1st. mode and 1.52Hz for the 2nd mode.

Figure 12 shows the time history of the external pressure coefficient predicted using a linearly efficient SVM. The external pressure coefficient in the windward region Ra changes from negative to positive after 10 seconds.

Figure 11: Natural modes

Figure 12: Predicted coefficient of external pressure

Figure 13: Deformation of membrane surface

Figure 14: Deformations in lateral side view

Figure 13 shows the shape of the membrane surface on X axis. The black dashed line represents the shape at the end of inflation, and the colored line represents the shape when the wind pressure is at its maximum. The red line is at 0.5 s, the yellow line at 29.5s, and the green line at 59.5s. For the constant external pressure coefficient shown in Figure 12(a), the top of the membrane rises to a maximum of 22 m and is displaced 2.3m on the upwind side. When the coefficient of external pressure is varied as shown in Figure 12(b), the top of the membrane rises to a maximum of 22 m and is displaced 2.3m upwind. As in the case of constant external pressure coefficient, the downwind side area is deformed inward from

the time of inflation. Figure 14 shows the deformations. There is almost no difference was observed in the deformation characteristics due to the difference in the external pressure coefficient settings.

Fig.15: Time histories of principal stress

Figure 15 shows the time history of principal stresses on the membrane surface. The vertical axis is the principal stress divided by the tensile strength. As shown in Figure 15(a), in the case of constant external pressure coefficient, the upwind element increases to about 90% of the tensile strength at the end of 120 seconds. On the other hand, in the case of variable external pressure coefficient shown in Figure 15(b), the stress begins to increase significantly from the end of inflation and exceeds approximately 97% at the 120 second point. Unlike the deformation characteristics, when the external pressure coefficient is varied, a gradual increase in the tensile strength is observed on the windward membrane surface.

5. Conclusion

In this study, the dynamic behavior of a pneumatic structure subjected to wind pressure depending deformation was numerically investigated. The results demonstrated that When the external pressure coefficient varies with deformation, the principal stress on the windward membrane surface responds strongly and reaches a value close to the tensile strength.

In further study, it is necessary to verify the validity of the learning results. We also plan to investigate the dynamic response of the air-membrane structure to wind loads with a return period of 500 years regarding the ultimate state.

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